

VOCABULARY IN RELATION TO PRIMARY STUDENTS

Khujanazarova Gulbakhor Gafurjanovna

Uzbek language and language teaching department

Fergana Polytechnic Institute

e-mail: g.xojanazarova@ferpi.uz

Annotation: This article discusses the significance of reading for pleasure in order to acquire vocabulary. It also discusses how children pick up new words when they are explicitly taught them, as well as how they pick up new terms accidentally through extensive reading and other language-rich activities. Certain terms can be thoroughly taught to kids, giving them the knowledge, they require to understand what they read. For the purpose of expanding their vocabulary, students who do not read independently must receive this direct instruction.

Key words: mnemonics, cognitive depth, acquisition, fluent language, researcher, to be concerned about, and to be maintained refreshed. It is widely acknowledged that vocabulary plays a crucial role in language learning. It is clear that vocabulary is essential to effective communication in any language, both in terms of comprehension and interaction.

Nonetheless, there has been an increase in interest in the shift toward the acknowledgment of the significance of lexical competence in the learning of second and/or foreign languages. Researchers studying foreign language acquisition have come to understand that the lexical dimension plays a crucial, if not pre-conditional, role in fluent language use and utilization across all skill levels. It can be argued that students whose target vocabulary is too little to achieve 95% coverage fail to comprehend the texts at a sufficient level. Additionally, Ellis has demonstrated that learning vocabulary is essential to learning grammar. In other words, by being able to comprehend the discourse presented in a book, learners are able to have a clearer understanding of the grammatical patterns.

That is to say, knowing the words in a text allows learners to understand the discourse, which in turn allows the grammatical patterning to become more transparent. In this sense too, Ellis underlines the critical importance of developing an adequate lexical approach since learners' skills in using the language is heavily dependent on the number of words they know, particularly in the early stages of

learning a foreign language. Learning vocabulary is a complex process in which the learner needs to acquire both the form and the variety of meanings of a given lexical item. An efficient language teacher can use selected vocabulary activities or can use integrated activities. All this depends upon ability and level of understanding and interest of the learners. There is no sure-fire remedy or method to enhance vocabulary in a day or two. A student's vocabulary bank can be enriched on a gradual basis and one should always show keen interest and enthusiasm in finding, learning and understanding new words.

However, many theories about vocabulary learning process were written, it still remains the matter of memory. Thus, there are several general principles for successful teaching, which are valid for any method. The principles are:

- aim – what is to be taught, which words, how many
- need – target vocabulary should respond students' real needs and interests
- frequent exposure and repetition
- meaningful presentation – clear and unambiguous denotation or reference should be assured

Learning vocabulary is a complex process. The students' aim to be reached in learning vocabulary process is primarily their ability to recall the word at will and to recognize it in its spoken and written form. Generally, knowing a word involves knowing its form and its meaning at the basic level. In deeper aspects it means the abilities to know its:

- 1) Meaning, i.e. relate the word to an appropriate object or context
- 2) Usage, i.e. knowledge of its collocations, metaphors and idioms, as well as style and register (the appropriate level of formality), to be aware of any connotations and associations the word might have
- 3) Word formation, i.e. ability to spell and pronounce the word correctly, to know any derivations (acceptable prefixes and suffixes),
- 4) Grammar, i.e. to use it in the appropriate grammatical form.

How words are remembered?

Unlike the learning of grammar, which is essentially a rule-based system, vocabulary knowledge is largely a question of accumulating individual items. The general rule seems to be a question of memory. And during the process of teaching and learning vocabulary an important problem occurs: How does memory work?

Researchers into the workings of memory distinguish between the following systems:

- short– term store
- working memory
- long– term memory

Short-term store is the brain capacity to hold a limited number of items of information for periods of time up to a few seconds. It is the kind of memory that is involved in repeating a word that you have just heard the teacher modelling. However, successful vocabulary learning involves more than holding words for a few seconds. To integrate words into long - term memory they need to be subjected to different kinds of operations.

Working memory means focusing on word long enough to perform operations on them. It means the information is manipulated via the senses from external sources and/or can be downloaded from the long- term memory. Material remains in working memory for about twenty seconds. The existence of articulator loop enables this new material processing. It works a bit like audiotape going round a round again. It assures the short- term store to be kept refreshed. The ability to hold a word in working memory is a good predictor of language learning aptitude. The better ability to hold words in working memory the smoother the process of learning foreign languages is.

Long –term memory can be seen as kind of filling system. Unlike working memory, which has a limited capacity and no permanent content, this kind of memory has an enormous capacity and its contents are durable over time. However, to ensure moving new materials into permanent long-term memory requires number of principles to be followed, described as followings:

- Repetition – repetition of encounters with a word is very important, useful and effective. If the word is met several times over space interval during reading activities, students have a very good chance to remember it for a long time.
- Retrieval - another kind of repetition. Activities, which require retrieval, such as using the new items in written tasks, help students to be able to recall it again in the future.
- Spacing - it is useful to split memory work over a period of time rather than to mass it together in a single block.

- Pacing – to respect different learning styles and pace, students should be ideally given the opportunity to do memory work individually.

- Use - putting words to use, preferably in an interesting way, is the best way of ensuring they are added to long – term memory. This is so called “Use it or lose it” principle.

- Cognitive depth - the more decisions students make about the word and the more cognitively demanding these decisions are, the better the word is remembered.

- Personal organizing - personalization significantly increased the probability that students will remember new items. It is achieved mainly through conversation and role-playing activities.

- Imaging – easily visualized words are better memorable than those that do not evoke with any pictures. Even abstract words can be associated with some mental image.

- Mnemonics – tricks to help retrieve items or rules that are stored in memory. The best kinds of mnemonics are visuals and keyword techniques.

- Motivation - strong motivation itself does not ensure that words will be remembered. Even unmotivated students remember words if they have to face appropriate tasks.

- Attention - it is not possible to improve vocabulary without a certain degree of conscious attention.

According to research, students’ vocabulary increases when they are exposed to new words through various language experiences, such as reading aloud, independent reading, and oral discussions. In addition, when students are exposed to a wide variety of reading genres, from biographies to fairy tales to how-to books, they learn different types of vocabulary.

To increase vocabulary in a day or two, there is no foolproof solution or technique. A student's vocabulary can be expanded gradually, and discovering, picking up, and comprehending new words should constantly be done with much excitement and zeal. Planning a wide range of exercises and activities is necessary for teachers teaching vocabulary through incidental, purposeful, and autonomous techniques. According to Richards, when teaching vocabulary words to students, teachers must take into account the students' ages, educational backgrounds, and areas of interest. The sociolinguistic context in which the words will be employed is something else the instructor should be aware of.

As one of the purposes of the present study is to report on the ways to collect data from children by using different data collection methods, the research identifies the advantages and disadvantages of each method by considering children's characteristics. The detailed report on the data collection procedures is hoped to shed some light into future research on children. Since there is no single method that is proved to be adequate or valid for data collection from children, it can be said that using multiple methods increases the validity of the findings.

List of references:

1. Ж. Жалолов. Г. Маҳкамova. Чет тил ўқитиш методикаси. Тошкент 2015 й.
2. Armbruster, B., Lehr, F., & Osborn, J. (2001). Put reading first: The research building blocks for teaching children to read. Jessup, MD: National Institute for Literacy.
3. Khujanazarova, G. (2023). PROFICIENCY IN COGNITIVE ACADEMIC LANGUAGE IS ESSENTIAL FOR THE LEARNER PARTICIPATION AND ENGAGEMENT THAT IS NECESSARY FOR SUBSEQUENT SUCCESS. Namangan davlat universiteti Ilmiy axborotnomasi, (6), 559-564.
4. Gulbakhor, K. (2023). Efficiency Factors in the Practical Use of the Uzbek Language. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, 18, 72-74.
5. Gofurjanovna, K. G. (2022). ON THE ROLE OF THE ETYMOLOGICAL PRINCIPLE IN THE TRANSLATION OF PHRASEOLOGIES. CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES, 3(06), 50-56.
6. Gofurjanovna, K. G. (2022). Linking Categories of Syntactic Units and Their Meaning in the Formation of Word Combinations. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, 9, 113-117.
7. Gofurjonovna, X. G. (2022). Restricting Technical Language. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(5), 364-367.
8. Khojanazarova, G. G. (2019). HAMLET IS THE MASTERPIECE OF ENGLISH LITERATURE. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND EDUCATION (pp. 56-57).
9. Gofurjonovna, H. G. (2016). Using an electronic educational-methodical complex in education. Наука и образование сегодня, (2 (3)), 69-70.

10. Oknazarov, O., Odilbekov, K., Saodatkadamov, M., & Khujanazarova, G. Anatomic changes of leaves' structure and plants' growth under influence of ultraviolet radiation of sun.
11. Хужаназарова, Г. Г. (2016). Дистанционное обучение в Европе. Academy, (6 (9)), 98-99.
12. Abdukadirov, U. N. (2022). BEST PRACTICE OF MOTIVATING SPEAKING ACTIVITIES FOR LOWER LEVELS. Экономика и социум, (12-1 (103)), 24-27.
13. Nazirovich, A. U. (2023). MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN HIGHER EDUCATION. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 20(2), 45-47.
14. Nazirovich, A. U. (2023). FEATURES OF THE TRANSLATION OF TECHNICAL TEXTS. Academia Science Repository, 4(05), 58-63.
15. Nazirovich, A. U. (2022). TURIZMGA OID ATAMALARNING LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. Conferencea, 256-258.

Research Science and Innovation House

